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Hemp Club

Competent and Connected
Clusters Unfold the Hemp
Industry Potential for the
European Bioeconomy

European Cluster Excellence Programme with ClusterXchange scheme connecting ecosystem and cities
COS-CLUSTER-2020-3-03

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WEBSITE
D5.2

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As part of task 5.2 “Website and media promotion”, the project website was designed and created with the **aim of being a primary point of reference for up-to-date information** on project partners, activities and results, providing information related to the project, main objectives and results, and acting as a communication channel for the target audience and a gateway for the CXC IT Tool. Aimed at developing a group of active members, the project website is also integrated with the project profiles on social media and the project newsletter.

Starting on 31 of May 2022, the project website can be accessed at the following address <https://hempclubproject.com/>. The website is updated regularly in the content and, if needed, in its structure (e.g. adding sub-sections) following partners’ and users’ suggestions and needs that may arise as the project is implemented.

To ensure project long-term sustainability, the project website will remain operational, maintained and updated during the entire duration of the project and at least 2 years after the project ends.

The information contained in the project website is structured in 9 sections, as follows:

1. HOME: contains a summary of project information, latest news and events.
2. ABOUT: contains the detailed project objectives and expected results.
3. PARTNERS: contains the list of the project partners with a direct link to their official website and their ECCP webpage.
4. DOCUMENTS: contains all the public documents produced within the HempClub project.
5. DISSEMINATION: contains information about past and future project events and the links to HempClub social media accounts.
6. NEWSLETTER: contains the link to subscribe to the project newsletter and a collection of past newsletters.
7. NEWS: contains relevant news on the hemp sector and related events. A link with the ECCP news published by the HempClub Partnership is also available
8. ClusterXchange: contains summary information about the CXC and a list of past and future exchanges.
9. CONTACT: contains the contact info of the HempClub Partnership.

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION: AIMS AND SCOPE OF THE PROJECT WEBSITE	4
2. ACCESS, HOSTING AND MANTAINANCE.....	4
2.1 Public access to the project website	4
2.2 Updates of the project website	4
2.3 Design, creation and maintenance of the project website	4
3 WEBSITE STRUCTURE.....	5
3.1 “HOME” section.....	5
2.2 “ABOUT” section.....	7
Hemp Club expected results will be the following:	8
2.3 “PARTNERS” section	8
2.4 “DOCUMENTS” section.....	9
2.5 “DISSEMINATION” section.....	10
2.6 “NEWSLETTER” section.....	10
2.7 “NEWS” section	12
2.8 “ClusterExchange” section	13
2.9 “CONTACT” section	14

1. INTRODUCTION: AIMS AND SCOPE OF THE PROJECT WEBSITE

This report describes the development and the structure of the project website as part of **task 5.2 “Website and media promotion”** within the HempClub project. This task aims to develop effective communication online channels (website, social media, newsletter, promotional campaigns) for the project target audiences, increasing project visibility, providing the latest news on achievements and results and supporting the implementation of “ClusterXchange” activities.

In this context, the HempClub project website was designed and created with the **aim** of:

- Being a primary point of reference for up-to-date information on project partners, activities and results;
- Providing an intuitive graphic interface for users to navigate the website and find all the information they need;
- Storing all the public reports (including deliverables) and other documents produced within the HempClub consortium;
- Hosting the HempClub outreach channels (i.e. social profiles and newsletter). Dedicated links to the HempClub social profiles are available on the project website and the subscription to the HempClub project newsletters, issued every 4 months, is also possible via the project website;
- Supporting the implementation of the ClusterXChange mobility scheme by providing a direct link with the ECCP and the CXC IT Tool;
- Stimulating the dialogue between stakeholders by promoting meetings and working group events;
- Ensuring the project’s long-term impact by remaining operational and updated at least 2 years after the project’s end.

The website will not be used as an internal project repository because there is an alternative repository in place (Google Drive shared folder).

The project website was created according to COSME programme specific requirements and according to the Visibility of the EU funding & obligation to use the EU emblem – Art 22.

2. ACCESS, HOSTING AND MAINTAINANCE

2.1 Public access to the project website

Starting on 31 of May 2022 (M4), the project website is publicly accessible at the following address <https://hempclubproject.com/>. The website is available in English.

2.2 Updates of the project website

INDAGROPOL manages the website and has the access to update the website

The Project Coordinator (PC) and other partners can require modifications and updates by sending an email to INDAGROPOL contact point. According to the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP), the **Communication task force** (Table 5 of DCP) is responsible for communication activities and act as a communication contact point. One of their main roles is to supply the content for the HempClub project website.

The website is updated regularly, on a bi-monthly basis or whenever deemed necessary, in the content (e.g. a new event is planned, a new public deliverable is produced, a new exchange is organized, etc..) and, if needed, in its structure (e.g. adding sub-sections) following partners’ and users’ suggestions and needs that may arise as the project is implemented.

2.3 Design, creation and maintenance of the project website

2.3.1 Website development

IND-AGRO-POL Association is the project partner responsible for the development and maintenance of the HempCluB project website and the website Administrator. According to the Grant Agreement (GA), the HempCluB project website (named website) design, set-up and maintenance was subcontracted by IND-AGRO-POL to a Developer by applying the public procurement rules.

This service will be provided during the period from the date 7.03.2022 and 31.01.2024 (date of completion of the HempCluB project). However, the Developer has also granted a warranty period of 2 years from the date of project completion and will fix the technical issues signaled by the Administrator within the warranty period, thus ensuring that the project website will remain operational and regularly maintained for at least 2 years after the project's end.

The Beneficiaries of the website are the partners of the HempCluB project consortium (named Beneficiaries), owning the programs, systems and IT tools, as well as their sources developed during the development process for the website. All the sections of the website were developed and agreed in collaboration with the Beneficiaries. The information contained in sections were provided by the Beneficiaries. A first version of the project structure was shared with all partners in mid April.

The Developer created systems and IT tools which will allow an easy updating and maintenance of the information on the website by the Administrator, as well as the modification of its structure. Also, The Developer will train the Administrator in the use and the development of this one, as well as in the use and development of the entire website, so that the Administrator will be able to update the project website even after the project's end.

The website was developed by using programming technology and databases in an open-source software systems (MySQL, PHP, HTML, Word Press CMS). The content of the website is in English. Developer created the graphical background for pages. The pages surface were covered with graphics of at least 20%. The website contains a gallery of images and the HempClub visual and informative material (logo, brochures, project presentation), provided by the project partners and uploaded by the Administrator via the Developer. Some information will be available to be downloaded and printed by the users. External links are also available to ensure a connection with other outreach tools.

3.2 Website administration

The Administrator of the project website is IND-AGRO-POL Association, monitoring the website traffic with detailed information about the source of access by categories of information and users.

The transfer of the website on the Administrator's hosting system will be performed by the Developer any time after the date on which the website is operational, at the Administrator's request.

The project website will be maintained during the project duration. Furthermore, the Developer will grant a warranty period of 2 years from the date of project completion and will fix the technical issues signaled by the Administrator within the warranty period. The Administrator, properly trained by the Developer, will also ensure that the project website will be updated regularly after the project's end.

3 WEBSITE STRUCTURE

The project website is composed of 9 sections which are described in detail in this paragraph.

3.1 "HOME" section

The "HOME" main section (figure 1) contains a summary of HempClub objectives as well as the latest events and news.

It, thus, contains the following information:

- Who We Are
- Our mission
- What we do
- Why hemp
- Implementing ClusterXChange

Fig. 1 “HOME” section – print screen

To increase the visibility of latest events and news, the home section also includes the following:

- PLANNED EXCHANGES, containing all the links to know more about the next exchange(s) planned by the HempClub Partnership;
- NEWS, reporting the latest news that can also be found in the “news” section (see paragraph 2.7)

A footer with the project logo, a short summary of the project, contact info, the EU flag and the funding disclaimer as well as the logos of all project partners is available in the “home” and in all the other project sections (Figure 2).

The Competent and Connected Clusters Unfold the Hemp Industry Potential for the European Bioeconomy (HempClub) project is an EU COSME project coordinated by LGCA bringing together 7 clusters and association operating in the primary hemp production, bioeconomy, mechatronics and green chemistry sectors from Italy, Czech Republic, Romania, Austria and Portugal.

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Fig. 2 Website footer – print screen

2.2 “ABOUT” section

ABOUT US

OBJECTIVES

The specific objectives of the HempClub partnership are:

- 1 Improve the **management skills** of cluster managers through a multidisciplinary training course that will involve at least 14 managers functional to achieving the Cluster Excellence Label certification for at least 4 clusters.
- 2 Strengthen **cluster excellence capacity** by improving the portfolio of business support services. At least 14 new services will be developed involving a minimum of 300 EU SMEs.
- 3 Facilitate **B2B and C2C collaborative activities** to strengthen interregional strategies for the bioeconomy, defining 20 new interregional cooperation projects and creating 2 value chains in the hemp sector.
- 4 **Organisation of at least 80 ClusterXchange opportunities** as short-term exchanges to enhance collaboration and networking activities between European organisations.
- 5 Promote **internationalisation, technology and knowledge transfer** through the activation of new opportunities for growth and capacity of excellence for clusters and their members.

Fig. 3 “ABOUT” section – print screen

This “ABOUT” section (figure 3) contains the specific objectives of the HempClub project, data about the project (budget, grant, project duration, start data), expected results, as follows:

The specific objectives of the Hemp Club partnership are:

- Improve the **management skills** of cluster managers through a multidisciplinary training course that will involve at least 14 managers functional to achieving the Cluster Excellence Label certification for at least 4 clusters.
- Strengthen **cluster excellence capacity** by improving the portfolio of business support services. At least 14 new services will be developed involving a minimum of 300 EU SMEs.
- **Facilitate B2B and C2C collaborative activities** to strengthen interregional strategies for the bioeconomy, defining 20 new interregional cooperation projects and creating 2 value chains in the hemp sector.
- **Organisation of at least 80 ClusterXchange opportunities** as short-term exchanges to enhance **collaboration** and **networking** activities between European organisations.
- Promote **internationalisation, technology and knowledge transfer** through the activation of new opportunities for growth and capacity of excellence for clusters and their members.

Hemp Club expected results will be the following:

- Involve at least **14 managers** in dedicated job training sessions towards strengthening managerial skills functional to achieving the **Cluster Excellence Label** certification.
- Develop a portfolio consisting of at least **14 new services** through a co-creation process involving a minimum of **300 European SME**.
- Contribute to the definition of at least **20 new interregional cooperation projects** and the creation of **2 value chains**.
- Reach over **300 SMEs**, raising awareness about the newly developed cluster strategies and **at least 80 ClusterXchange** opportunities to better provide support services to industrial actors and SMEs operating in the hemp sector.
- Participate in **at least 20 EU events and fair** on the bioeconomy and industrial-hemp sector contribute to maximising the project’s impact, ensuring its sustainability also after the project end.

2.3 “PARTNERS” section

Fig. 4 “PARTNERS” section – print screen

The Hemp Club project partners are (figure 4):

- LOMBARDY GREEN CHEMISTRY CLUSTER - Italy

- CZECH HEMP CLUSTER - Czech Republic
- PRODUTECH - PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES CLUSTER – Portugal
- SPRING - ITALIAN CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY CLUSTER – Italy
- STANDORTAGENTUR TIROL GMBH: CLUSTER MECHATRONICS TIROL – Austria
- IND-AGRO-POL – Romania
- FEDERCANAPA – Italy.

The users can find on this section a link to the official website of each partner. This section also aims to build a connection between the HempClub website and the ECCP website, by including the link to the ECCP details for each partner.

2.4 “DOCUMENTS” section

Fig. 5 “DOCUMENTS” section – print screen

In this section the main HempClub communication materials in pdf format are published (figure 5):

- HEMPCLUB PROJECT PRESENTATION
- BROCHURE HEMPCLUB PRINT VERSION
- BROCHURE HEMPCLUB WEB VERSION.

The following sub-sections are also planned in order to further include all the public material produced within the HempClub project:

- Public deliverables: all public deliverables produced during the project implementation will be published in this section;
- Events: all the slides presented during public events/webinars organized by the Partnership will be available in this section, including slides presented by speakers (after receiving their formal approval for publication).

- Networking: this section will include all the institutional presentations of the visitors and hosts within the HempClub Partnerships (after receiving their formal approval for publication), acting as a point of reference for hemp operators to find possible partners and collaborations.

2.5 “DISSEMINATION” section

In this section, the user can find detailed information about the future events and the past events organized or assisted by the HempClub project, as shown in the figure 6.

Besides general information on the event (where, when, what), future events include the link for registration to the event, while past events have a link to further information (e.g. press release, published material of the event, official page of the event).

Moreover, the user has the possibility to connect to social accounts (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn) of the Hemp Club project.

Fig. 6 “DISSEMINATION” section – print screen

2.6 “NEWSLETTER” section

In this section (figure 7), the user has the possibility to subscribe to the HempClub newsletter, in order to know more about the potential of hemp for biobased applications and stay updated on HempClub project activities and events. Indeed, by using the “REGISTER” button, the user is asked to fill a form requiring his email address, first name and last name (figure 8). The newsletter registration form is managed by MailChimp in compliance with GDPR rules.

Fig. 7 "NEWSLETTER" section – print screen

The form is titled "HempClub newsletter" and is set against a light gray background with the Hemp Club logo at the top. It contains three input fields: "Email Address", "First Name", and "Last Name". Below these fields is a dark gray "Subscribe" button.

HempClub newsletter

Email Address

First Name

Last Name

Subscribe

Fig. 8 Form to subscribe to Hemp Club newsletter

All the newsletters issued from the beginning of the project are also available in this section under the “OUR NEWSLETTER COLLECTION” subsection (figure 7).

2.7 “NEWS” section

In this section, the platform administrators post the most important news regarding the HempClub activities and the future events, as it is shown the figure 9. It also included a link to HempClub news posted on the ECCP website.

Fig. 9 “NEWS” section – print screen

So far, 4 news were published. Each news is presented shortly and the user can view or download the entire news using the button “Read article” highlighted in green. The entire news are presented with recent posts links and related posts links. Furthermore, the user can leave a reply regarding to news (Fig. 9), encouraging open access research and fostering discussion between the HempClub community.

[Download here the call for training.](#)

Category: News • By hempclub • August 31, 2022 • Leave a comment

PREVIOUS

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July 6, 2022

Circular Bioeconomy - Opportunities for the rural areas
June 7, 2022

HempClub project for a sustainable EU bioeconomy
May 27, 2022

Future events
May 26, 2022

Recent comments

Fig. 10 Web page with recent posts, related posts and leave a reply

2.8 “ClusterExchange” section

This section contains summary information about the ClusterXChange pilot scheme. This information are compliant with the content described on the CXC webpage. In particular, the users can find information about the ClusterXchange pilot scheme, namely (figure 11):

- What is an exchange?
- Who can participate?
- How long is the duration of an exchange?
- Contribution fundings
- How can I participate?
- Our objectives

Furthermore, this section contains useful links for the user, such as:

- European Cluster Collaboration platform: the European online hub for industry clusters;
- HempClub Partnership: to know more about the project and its CXC initiatives;
- CXC homepage: to know more about the CSC mobility scheme;
- CXC IT Tool: to register as a host or visiting organization.

Finally, this section includes all the planned and past exchanges organized by the HempClub project.

Fig. 11 “ClusterExchange” section - print screen

2.9 “CONTACT” section

This section (figure 12) contains the contact information of the Hemp Club project. Besides providing the email address, it is also possible to complete an online form with user’s requests.

Fig. 12 “CONTACT” section - print screen